

A Conceptual Model for Agile Practices Adoption

Amadeu Silveira Campanelli, Fernando Silva Parreiras

¹LAIS Laboratory of Advanced Information Systems, FUMEC University
Av. Afonso Pena 3880 30130009 Belo Horizonte MG Brazil
Master's Thesis - Work in Progress

Abstract. *The software development industry has been adopting agile methods and practices instead of traditional software development methods because they are more flexible and can bring benefits such as handling requirements changes, productivity gains, frequent releases and business strategy focus. This work proposes a model for agile process data representation to show the relationships between agile components (principles, methods, practices, techniques, roles and work products) to allow organizations to define the strategy of agile practices adoption to achieve their business goals. Through competency questions the model has been validated using Scrum method data as the initial dataset. Future work includes the addition of more agile methods to the model repository and the validation of organization tailored methods using the model. Keywords: agile practices, agile adoption, practices selection, agile adoption model*

1. Introduction

Agile methods for software development have been increasingly used by the software industry based on a set of advantages such as accelerate time to market, quality and productivity increase, IT/business alignment improvement, welcoming changes and managing priorities reorganization compared to traditional software development methods [Nishijima and Dos Santos 2013, Qumer and Henderson-Sellers 2006b, Jyothi and Rao 2011, VersionOne 2013]. Even though the benefits of agile methods are worth and have been proved by scientific and market researches [Jyothi and Rao 2011, Moniruzzaman and Hossain 2013, Ahmed and Sidky 2009, VersionOne 2013] the complexity of adopting them is high because of organization culture, resistance to changes and need for upper management sponsorship and involvement [Sidky et al. 2007, VersionOne 2013].

Based on the current challenges of software development, agile approaches are interesting options to achieve quality, project budget control, align with organization's business strategy and deliver value frequently and continuously [Saleh 2013, VersionOne 2013, Nishijima and Dos Santos 2013]. The choice of the adoption strategy of agile approaches is a key component to success in order to get the organization to take advantage of the benefits brought by agility [Sidky et al. 2007, Soundararajan et al. 2012] and to overcome the common issues found on the adoption process and achieve the organization's business goals [Qumer and Henderson-Sellers 2008].

Research on agile adoption normally try to tailor the agile method selecting practices to achieve the organization needs, since full agile method adoption can be an overkill for organizations or require lots of resources [Qumer and Henderson-Sellers 2008]. Some research analyze which agile practices were the most adopted ones based the literature and on industry surveys [Kurapati et al. 2012, Jalali and Wohlin 2010,

Abbas et al. 2010, Manyam and Kurapati 2012], others take into account which maturity level the organization wants to adopt to select the appropriate agile practices [Ahmed and Sidky 2009, Qumer and Henderson-Sellers 2008], some select agile practices to adopt based on project characteristics [Saleh 2013] and there are also research on practices selection based on strategy graphs representing the relationships between strategies at multiple organization levels [Esfahani et al. 2011].

This paper proposes a model to store information about agile principles, methods, practices and correlated information to allow organizations to understand their current practices versus agile practices and define the strategy of agile practices adoption to achieve the organization's goals.

The remainder of this paper is structured as follows. Section 2 presents a literature review on agility, agile methods and related work regarding agile practices adoption strategies. On Section 3 the model is defined and on Section 4 the model is validated and discussed. Section 5 summarizes the findings, states limitations and opportunities for future work.

2. Related Work

2.1. Agile Manifesto

The Agile Manifesto [Beck et al. 2001] has consolidated values and principles from existing agile methods and approaches and made the agile movement stronger and organized on the software development industry. Agile values are: individuals and interactions, working software, customer collaboration and responding to change.

Agile principles are:

- Early and continuous delivery of valuable software;
- Change is welcome;
- Deliver frequently;
- People interaction (business and developers);
- Motivated people;
- Face-to-face communication;
- Working software is progress;
- Constant pace;
- Technical excellence and good design;
- Simplicity;
- Self-organized teams;
- Continuous improvement.

Agile methods are in their essence based on values and principles defined on the Agile Manifesto [Beck et al. 2001] and composed by agile practices [Jalali and Wohlin 2010]. Agile practices should help accomplish the agile principles on a method and can be grouped into management practices, software process practices and software development practices [Lee and Yong 2013]. Example of agile practices are: pair programming, daily stand-up meetings, unit testing and open work area. The current mainstream agile methods are: eXtreme Programming (XP), Scrum [Schwaber and Sutherland 2011], Kanban, Lean e Feature-Driven Development (FDD). Scrum is currently the most adopted one [VersionOne 2013]. Each method focus on specific values and there is no standard on how a method should implement its agility.

Handling unstable requirements, delivering working software in short time frames, with high quality and under budget are the main characteristics of agile methods compared to traditional ones [Jyothi and Rao 2011]. Being agile is to be able to rapidly adapt to change in a flexible way [Qumer and Henderson-Sellers 2006b]. The capability is reflected by the attributes of flexibility, velocity, leanness, learning and response to change. According to [Qumer and Henderson-Sellers 2006b] agility can be defined as the ability to accommodate changes (expected or not) quickly in a dynamic environment being simple, economic and having quality in a short iteration strategy applying previous knowledge and generating new ones on this experience. Handling unstable requirements, delivering working software in short time frames, with high quality and under budget are the main characteristics of agile methods compared to traditional ones [Jyothi and Rao 2011].

2.2. Agile Practices Adoption

The problem of selecting agile practices to be adopted by organizations is a known problem and researchers have been working on it but there is still no definitive answer for the theme [Kurapati et al. 2012, Madi et al. 2011, Abbas et al. 2010, Esfahani et al. 2011, Ahmed and Sidky 2009]. Not all organizations are ready to implement agile in a full manner regarding to both on cultural and technical aspects [Qumer and Henderson-Sellers 2008]. Besides these changes demand a considerable financial investment and also have a big impact on the daily tasks performed by the teams. The agile adoption could be partial and also keep other practices the organization currently adopts in place and combined with the new set of practices to make the organization more successful.

Agile methods are not always used completely in an organization because of specific needs and constraints. The agile practices selection allow organizations to best achieve their goals [Kurapati et al. 2012]. There is no final academic solution on how the practices selection should happen. Organizations can adopt agile in multiple ways, depending on their business goals, culture and resources [Abbas et al. 2010]. The agile practices adoption can also be unique per organization taking into account the areas of the development process the organization wants to improve. Normally organizations need help choosing the right combination of practices for their environment. The association/correspondence between agile values and the organization culture defines which set of practices could be followed by this organization [Madi et al. 2011].

A systematic review of the research literature on use of agile in global software engineering presented a list of agile practices used or referenced by the analyzed papers [Jalali and Wohlin 2010]. A survey on agile practices adoption proposed to understand which practices have been used by the software development industry [Kurapati et al. 2012]. This survey analysed practices adoption at the project and organization levels and also defined the association between practices.

A work focused on the quality aspects of the agile practices showed the main agile practices associated with high quality of the software product [de Azevedo Santos et al. 2011]. Factor analysis was applied to group 58 agile practices and found 15 factors and checked the correlation between them finding application of quality assurance and iterative and incremental practices had a high success rate [Abbas et al. 2010].

SAAP (Strategic Analysis for Agile Practices) framework [Esfahani et al. 2011] was proposed with the intent to associate business goals to the selection process for agile practices adoption. SAAP extended Situation Method Engineering and used concepts from Balanced Scorecard (BSC). This work linked the selection of agile practices to the organization's business goals.

Sidky Agile Measurement Index (SAMI) [Ahmed and Sidky 2009] showed the adoption of agile practices based on an agile maturity model. SAMI is a 5-step road map to guide teams adopting based in 5 values considered essential to agility: enhancing communication and collaboration, delivering software early and continuously, developing high quality, working software in an efficient and integrated manner, respond to change through multiple levels of feedback and establishing an environment to sustain agility. SAMI is not based on any specific agile method such as XP, Scrum or Crystal, but instead, uses agile values and principles to define the path to agility.

The analysis of papers and books from Agile Manifesto signatories using content analysis [Madi et al. 2011] identified the key agile values and how frequent they were mentioned on the literature. The agile key values obtained by this work were: Flexibility, Customer-centric, Working Software, Collaboration, Simplicity, Communication, Natural, Learning, Pragmatism and Adaptability. A methodology to select the best agile practices for projects based on the association between project's characteristics and the abilities of the agile practices has been defined [Saleh 2013] and the key project's areas analyzed in the work were team size, iteration duration and distributed teams.

An empirical study identified common adopted practices, listed practices that normally are used together and correlated the customer satisfaction after adopting the practices [Manyam and Kurapati 2012]. This work also tried to identify adaptation by organizations on the adopted practices.

3. Conceptual Model Proposal

Even though the benefits obtained of agile adoption have been proved by scientific and market researches [Jyothi and Rao 2011, Moniruzzaman and Hossain 2013, Ahmed and Sidky 2009, VersionOne 2013], the adoption process complexity cannot be forgotten since it requires lots of effort from the organization and teams, cultural adaptation, deals with egos and resistance to changes and demands upper management sponsorship [Abbas et al. 2010, VersionOne 2013]. Besides that, there are cases in which some of the practices available on the mainstream agile methods do not make sense for an organization. The value an agile practice (such as continuous integration or refactoring) aggregates to the organization development process also varies. Then adopting all the practices proposed by an agile method at once means that the organization needs to spend effort and resources adopting it and the value brought by this adoption varies and however there is no guarantee the investment made is maximized.

These types of challenges motivated academic researches on agile practices adoption and practices selection in order to generate a custom/tailored software development process more consistent with the organization's values, culture, reality and strategies [Abbas et al. 2010]. This way the organization will only spend effort adopting the practices that aggregate value to the development process and help to achieve their business goals.

The agile practices adoption strategy seems to make the adoption process simpler and brings the benefits of being agile achievable by the organization earlier in the process [Sidky et al. 2007, Qumer and Henderson-Sellers 2008]. It can generate confidence on the teams and bring organizational support for further adoption and more process improvement initiatives.

3.1. Competency Questions

In this context an organization needs to answer questions to help it to understand how agile methods or practices can be adopted, what is the strategy that better fits the organization's needs, which agile practices to adopt and how do the organization's currently practices fit on an agile structure (agile principles, methods and practices). Follow 4 questions an organization might ask when evaluating the adoption of agile practices. These questions are going to be used to validate the proposed model.

- **Q1:** Which are the agile practices an organization needs to adopt if their business goals focus on agile principle X?
- **Q2:** Which are the agile principles followed by an organization adopting method Y?
- **Q3:** Which are the agile principles followed by an organization using a set of agile practices Z?
- **Q4:** Which are the correlated agile practices that can be adopted by an organization currently using a set of agile practices W?

3.2. The Model

The proposed conceptual model for agile process data representation for this work can be seen on Figure 1. The main goal of the model is to help organizations to understand and make decisions regarding agile practices adoption or selection and/or how evolve their current software development processes using agile practices. The idea represented by the model is the relationship between agile components (principles, methods, practices, techniques, roles and work products) in a way the existing agile methods or organization tailored software development processes can be mapped using it and analyzed based on the organization business goals' point of view.

Model components:

- **Agile Principle:** The agile principles have been the structure behind the Agile Manifesto [Beck et al. 2001], define what is to be agile and guide agile methods. The Agile Manifesto is based on 12 principles listed on Section 2. Agile principles should be used on the model to map set of practices to business goals the organizations want to achieve.
- **Method:** Agile methods are different ways to apply the agile philosophy and can share characteristics. Each method has own terminology, set of practices (some of them can be found on other methods), tactics, roles and coverage of the software development life cycle. Example of agile methods are: Scrum and XP. This entity should only represent the mainstream agile methods available on the literature and the model will use agile methods to provide a basis for comparison to the current software development processes on the organizations.

Figure 1. Entity-Relationship of proposed model to represent agile principles, methods, practices and related components.

- **Practice:** An agile practice is an activity used to help implement agile principles or values. Examples of practices are: daily standup, collective ownership, short releases and small teams. The relationship between agile principles and practices should allow organizations to choose which practices should be adopted based on the organizations business goals and how the practices correlate with each other to fulfill the defined goals.
- **Role:** The role is the person or group of people defined to execute or participate on a practice. For Scrum the roles are: product owner, scrum master and development team. Roles are associated with agile methods and practices and can provide guidance on how the organization should build teams for agile practices adoption.
- **Technique:** Technique is a way to execute a task for an agile practice. Different techniques can be applied to execute the same task and it can be defined by the agile method. Examples of techniques for the backlog prioritization agile practice are: Kano Analysis, Theme Screening and Relative Weighting. The technique of choice for an agile practice will depend on which will make more sense for the organization’s culture, how the organization’s software development process is structured and the learning curve of the technique versus existing knowledge on the organization.
- **Work Product:** Work product is an artifact generated by a technique in an agile practice or method. Examples of work products for Scrum are: Product Backlog, Sprint Backlog and Sprint Burndown Chart. Work products should provide guidance on which artifacts need to be created during the selected practices adoption.

The model repository was implemented in a SQL database representing the model classes and their relationships. The repository is able to respond to queries based on the

data stored on the tables and the data collection to feed the model is going to be based of the review of literature on agile methods and practices and also reference web sites on the mainstream agile methods.

4. Discussion

The model implementation at this stage of the research is a proof of concept and only Scrum data have been added to the model repository so far. The data has been loaded based on the Agile Manifesto [Beck et al. 2001] and on the literature on Scrum [Schwaber and Sutherland 2011, Deemer et al. 2010, Cohn 2009, Qumer and Henderson-Sellers 2006a] and adapted in order to be generalized and possible to be compared to other agile methods in the future. A sample of the data loaded into the repository can be seen on Figure 2.

Agile Principles		Practices	
1	Change is welcome	1	Short Releases
2	Constant pace	2	Features List
3	Continuous improvement	3	Daily StandUp
4	Deliver frequently	4	Small Teams
5	Early and continuous delivery of valuable software	5	Iteration Planning
6	Face-to-face communication	6	Iteration Review
7	Motivated people	7	Retrospective
8	People interaction (business and developers)		
9	Self-organized teams		
10	Simplicity		
11	Technical excellence and good design		
12	Working software is progress		

Figure 2. Agile principles and practices stored on the model repository for the proof of concept.

In order to validate the proposed model the competency questions defined on Section 3.1 against the proof of concept repository. Follow a demonstration of the queries to retrieve information from the model repository and the results according to the proof of concept dataset. The proof of concept was implemented as a Windows console application to output the answers for the competency questions.

The queries for the questions are represented on Table 1 and all the results are listed on Table 2. The agile principle considered for question **Q1** was continuous improvement and the Scrum practices retrieved from the model repository were 'Daily StandUp', 'Iteration Review' and 'Retrospective' to follow the continuous improvement principle.

In order to answer question **Q2** Scrum was considered the adopted agile method and the result listed all practices used by Scrum. Question **Q3** result showed that the practices 'daily standup', 'feature list', 'short releases' are involved in 7 out of 12 agile principles. These practices can be a good initial choice for organizations seeking to be agile and wanting to start to understand how the agile principles work.

The result for question **Q4** showed practices are the ones involved on the same agile principles as 'small teams' and 'daily standup'. The practices listed should be the first choice for adoption if an organization currently adopts 'small teams' and 'daily standup' practices.

Question	Query
Q1: Which are the agile practices an organization needs to adopt if their business goals focus on agile principle 'Continuous Improvement'?	SELECT P.Name FROM Practice AS P INNER JOIN PrinciplePractice AS PP on P.ID = PP.PracticeID INNER JOIN Principle AS Pr ON Pr.id = P.PrincipleID WHERE Pr.Name = 'Continuous improvement'
Q2: Which are the agile principles followed by an organization adopting method 'Scrum'?	SELECT P.Name FROM Practice AS P INNER JOIN MethodPractice AS MP on P.ID = MP.PracticeID INNER JOIN Method AS M ON M.id = MP.MethodID WHERE M.Name = 'Scrum' ORDER BY P.Name
Q3: Which are the agile principles followed by an organization using a set of agile practices: daily standup, feature list and short releases?	SELECT Pr.Name FROM Principle AS Pr INNER JOIN PrinciplePractice AS PP on Pr.ID = PP.PrincipleID INNER JOIN Practice AS P ON P.id = PP.PracticeID WHERE P.Name IN ('daily standup', 'feature list', 'short releases') ORDER BY Pr.Name
Q4: Which are the correlated agile practices that can be adopted by an organization currently using a set of agile practices: iteration planning and small teams?	SELECT DISTINCT P.Name FROM Practice AS P INNER JOIN PrinciplePractice AS PP ON P.id = PP.PracticeID WHERE PP.PrincipleID IN (SELECT Pr.ID FROM Principle AS Pr INNER JOIN PrinciplePractice AS PP ON Pr.ID = PP.PrincipleID INNER JOIN Practice AS P ON P.id = PP.PracticeID WHERE P.Name IN ('small teams', 'daily standup')) AND P.Name NOT IN ('small teams', 'daily standup') ORDER BY P.Name

Table 1. Queries for all the questions

The answers for the competency questions demonstrated that the model can support organization to understand how agile components correlate to each other and how agile practices can be mapped to organizations existing practices and business goals. More than that, it showed the proposed model establishes relationships between important components of agile methods and practices that can be used to guide organizations on the decision of which agile practices to adopt considering their business goals and their current software development process or current agile practices already adopted.

5. Conclusion

This paper proposed a model to store information about agile principles, methods, practices and correlated information to allow organizations to understand their current practices versus agile practices and define the strategy of agile practices adoption to achieve the organization's goals. The model was validated based on the competency questions defined providing answers to questions organizations ask or need to respond in order to decide how they should adopt agile practices and how their current method is compliant with agile principles and methods.

This research is still in progress and there are several limitations including the interface to retrieve the data from the repository, the availability of only Scrum data on the model repository and the lack of real organization data to be validated against the model. Future work based on this paper can include the addition of more agile methods to be model, the model validation with organizations intending to adopt agile methods or practices and the model usage to check how organizations business goals map to agile

Question	Answer
Q1	Daily Standup, Iteration Review and Retrospective
Q2	Daily Standup, Features List, Iteration Planning, Iteration Review, Retrospective, Short Releases and Small Teams
Q3	Change is welcome, Continuous improvement, Deliver frequently, Early and continuous delivery of valuable software, Face-to-face communication, People interaction (business and developers) and Working software is progress
Q4	Iteration Planning, Iteration Review, Retrospective

Table 2. Answers for all the questions

principles and practices.

References

- Abbas, N., Gravell, A. M., and Wills, G. B. (2010). Using factor analysis to generate clusters of agile practices (a guide for agile process improvement). In *Agile Conference (AGILE), 2010*, pages 11–20. IEEE.
- Ahmed, E.-M. and Sidky, A. (2009). 25 percent ahead of schedule and just at step 2 of the sami. In *Agile Conference, 2009. AGILE'09.*, pages 162–169. IEEE.
- Beck, K., Beedle, M., van Bennekum, A., Cockburn, A., Cunningham, W., Fowler, M., Grenning, J., Highsmith, J., Hunt, A., Jeffries, R., Kern, J., Marick, B., Martin, R. C., Mellor, S., Schwaber, K., Sutherland, J., and Thomas, D. (2001). Manifesto for agile software development. <http://agilemanifesto.org/>. Accessed: 2014-03-21.
- Cohn, M. (2009). *Succeeding with agile: software development using scrum*. Addison-Wesley Professional. ISBN 978-0321579362.
- de Azevedo Santos, M., de Souza Bermejo, P. H., de Oliveira, M. S., and Tonelli, A. O. (2011). Agile practices: An assessment of perception of value of professionals on the quality criteria in performance of projects. *Journal of Software Engineering & Applications*, 4(12).
- Deemer, P., Benefield, G., Larman, C., and Vodde, B. (2010). The scrum primer. <http://assets.scrumtraininginstitute.com/downloads/1/scruprimer121.pdf>. Accessed: 2014-04-09.
- Esfahani, H. C., Eric, S., and Annosi, M. C. (2011). Towards the strategic analysis of agile practices. In *CAiSE Forum*, pages 155–162.
- Jalali, S. and Wohlin, C. (2010). Agile practices in global software engineering-a systematic map. In *Global Software Engineering (ICGSE), 2010 5th IEEE International Conference on*, pages 45–54. IEEE.
- Jyothi, V. E. and Rao, K. N. (2011). Effective implementation of agile practices ingenious and organized theoretical framework. *IJACSA - International Journal of Advanced Computer Science and Applications*, 2(3):41–48.

- Kurapati, N., Manyam, V. S. C., and Petersen, K. (2012). Agile software development practice adoption survey. In *Agile Processes in Software Engineering and Extreme Programming*, pages 16–30. Springer.
- Lee, S. and Yong, H.-S. (2013). Agile software development framework in a small project environment. *Journal of Information Processing Systems*, 9(1).
- Madi, T., Dahalin, Z., and Baharom, F. (2011). Content analysis on agile values: A perception from software practitioners. In *Software Engineering (MySEC), 2011 5th Malaysian Conference in*, pages 423–428. IEEE.
- Manyam, V. S. C. and Kurapati, N. (2012). Empirical investigation on adoption and adaptation of agile practices. Master's thesis, Blekinge Institute of Technology.
- Moniruzzaman, A. B. M. and Hossain, S. A. (2013). Comparative study on agile software development methodologies. *CoRR*.
- Nishijima, R. T. and Dos Santos, J. G. (2013). The challenge of implementing scrum agile methodology in a traditional development environment. *INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF COMPUTERS & TECHNOLOGY*, 5(2):98–108.
- Qumer, A. and Henderson-Sellers, B. (2006a). Comparative evaluation of xp and scrum using the 4d analytical tool (4-dat). In *Proceedings of the European and Mediterranean conference on information systems*, volume 2006.
- Qumer, A. and Henderson-Sellers, B. (2006b). Crystallization of agility back to basics. In Filipe, J., Shishkov, B., and Helfert, M., editors, *ICSOFT (2)*, pages 121–126. INSTICC Press.
- Qumer, A. and Henderson-Sellers, B. (2008). A framework to support the evaluation, adoption and improvement of agile methods in practice. *Journal of Systems and Software*, 81(11):1899–1919.
- Saleh, M. H. (2013). Methodology for selection of agile practices. Master's thesis, American University of Sharjah.
- Schwaber, K. and Sutherland, J. (2011). The scrum guide. <http://www.scrum.org>. Accessed: 2014-04-19.
- Sidky, A., Arthur, J., and Bohner, S. (2007). A disciplined approach to adopting agile practices: the agile adoption framework. *Innovations in systems and software engineering*, 3(3):203–216.
- Soundararajan, S., Arthur, J. D., and Balci, O. (2012). A methodology for assessing agile software development methods. In *Agile Conference (AGILE), 2012*, pages 51–54. IEEE.
- VersionOne (2013). 8th annual state of agile development survey. <http://stateofagile.versionone.com>. Accessed: 2014-03-30.